

Reading assessment practices of kindergarten to grade 3 teachers

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Abstract

Reading is one of the most frequently measured abilities (Smith, 2004). Yet it is only fairly recently that an empirically grounded set of Standards for the Assessment of Reading and Writing was established by the National Council of Teachers of English (NCTE) Standards for the Assessment of Reading and Writing NCTE/IRA Joint Task Force on Assessment. The Standards, which are aimed to guide the assessment of teaching and learning of literacy on the 21st century, emphasized the crucial role of teachers in the preparation and conduct of literacy assessment as well as the strategic use of assessment results. There is therefore a need to investigate the reading / literacy assessment practices of teachers. In this study, such concern is explored by surveying the assessment practices of Kindergarten to Grade 3 teachers in a Teacher Education Institution (TEI) Laboratory School and in a Non-laboratory School. The study sought to determine 1) how frequently the reading / literacy teachers assess their students; 2) how frequently they assess each of the fourteen domains of literacy; 3) what are the different types of literacy assessments that the teachers use and how often they use them in the classroom; 4) at what level of schooling they assess particular literacy domains; and 5) how they use the assessment results. The results show that the Kindergarten through Grade 3 teachers in the Lab and Non-lab School 1) assess students' reading skills at a daily basis; 2) assess similar reading / literacy domains with comparable frequency and at similar levels of schooling, and 3) use the assessment results primarily for reporting purposes. On the other hand, they differ in that the Laboratory School emphasized the assessment of higher levels of reading comprehension starting from the Kindergarten level and use such innovative assessment procedures as portfolio and anecdotal records more frequently compared to the teachers in the Non-laboratory School. Such findings are discussed within the context of the NCTE-IRA Standards for the Assessment of Reading and Writing, with a caveat that these standards should also be examined in light of local contexts and practices.

Keywords: Reading; Reading assessment practices; Kindergarten; Grade 3; Teachers.

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Introduction

Classroom assessment should play a role in describing and supporting students' reading development. Despite this role, classroom assessment has only recently been a focus of systematic investigation, and to complicate matters, there is disagreement as to the function and value of specific classroom assessment. – Peter P. Afflerbach and Byeong-Yeong Cho (2011)

Reading is one of the most frequently measured abilities (Smith, 2004). In fact, according to Venezky (1987), there is “no other component of the curriculum [that] has been subjected throughout its history to such intense controversy over both its basic methods and its content” (as cited by Campbell, 2001). Yet, it has only been in recent years that the “disagreement” on the function and value of specific classroom assessments of reading has been systematically investigated and addressed. One of these

initiatives involves the articulation of empirically-grounded standards on literacy assessment. In the United States, the Standards for the Assessment of Reading and Writing were crafted in 1994 and revised in 2007 by the National Council of Teachers in English (NCTE) and the International Reading Association (IRA) based on at least forty years of research, “*to improve the quality of assessment through informed decisions about assessing the teaching and learning of literacy in 21st-century classrooms*” (USAID, 2018).

Although the Revised Standards for the Assessment of Reading and Writing (2009) emphasized the nature of reading assessment as a social and political process involving a multiplicity of stakeholders, it reiterated the crucial role of teachers in the process. Standard 2 states that “*the teacher is the most important agent of assessment.*” As most educational assessment takes place in the classroom, the teachers mediate the assessment process and determine, to a large extent, its success or failure in relation to the purposes for which the assessment is conducted. Standard 2 emphasized that “*teachers design, assign, observe, collaborate in, and interpret the work of students in their classrooms. They assign meaning to interactions and evaluate the information that they receive and create in these settings. In short, teachers are the primary agents, not passive consumers, of assessment information. It is their ongoing, formative assessments that primarily influence students’ learning.*” Given this critical role of teachers in the assessment of reading and writing, it is important to explore their assessment practices.

This study aims to investigate the reading assessment practices of Kindergarten as well as Grades 1, 2, and 3 teachers in two schools: one is a laboratory school of a teacher education institution in a university, while the other is a non-laboratory school. Both schools are private and sectarian, i.e., they are both founded as Christian institutions whose vision and mission relate to academic excellence in the context of Christian-grounded values. Laboratory schools are affiliated with teacher education institutions (TEIs), which maintain a reciprocal relationship with the laboratory school by providing technical and academic support through the sustained provision of student teachers who engage in a variety of apprenticeship experiences in order to practice the theoretical and pedagogical insights they learned from the TEI, from observing classes to the conduct of student teaching practicum.

The study focuses on five aspects of the Assessment of Reading and Writing, particularly in the early grades. It focuses on identifying 1) the frequency of the teachers’ reading assessments of the 14 literacy domains; 2) the different types of literacy assessments that the teachers use and how often they use them in the classroom; 3) the level in which they use the assessment types; and 4) how they use the assessment results.

In this study, reading is defined in the broader context of the fourteen domains of literacy emphasized by the Department of Education. These include the following: oral language, alphabet knowledge, phonological awareness, book and print knowledge, phonics and word recognition, fluency, spelling, handwriting, composing, reading comprehension, listening comprehension, grammar awareness, vocabulary, and attitudes toward reading, language, and literature.

Statement of the Problem

The primary purpose of the study is to identify and evaluate the assessment practices of the classroom reading teachers from Kindergarten to Grade 3 in accordance with the Standards for the Assessment of Reading and Writing set by the NCTE and the IRA and the fourteen domains of literacy that are currently emphasized by the Department of Education. It specifically aims to answer the following research questions:

1. How often do K-3 reading / literacy teachers assess their students?
2. How often do K-3 reading / literacy teachers assess the 14 literacy domains?
3. What assessment types do they use and how frequently do they use them?
4. What teacher-made test types are used by K-3 reading teachers and how frequently do they use them?

5. At what level of schooling do they test the following?
 - a) Literacy domains emphasized in K-3
 - b) Various levels of comprehension
6. How do K-Grade 3 teachers use the assessment results?

Methodology

Participants

A descriptive research methodology was used for this study. A survey was administered to a selected sample of the teachers in the Kindergarten to Grade 3 in two schools: a teacher education institution laboratory school in the province and a private school in Metro Manila that is not associated with any teacher training institution (henceforth termed non-laboratory school). Twenty-four teachers responded to the survey, fourteen from the laboratory school and ten from the non-laboratory school. Specific information about the respondents is shown below.

Table 1. Respondents’ profile

Profile	Laboratory School	Non-laboratory School
Sample (n)	14	10
Sex	14 females	10 females
Average age	39	26
Academic degree	Undergraduate: BEEd-ECE: 43% BEEd-PSEd: 7% BEEd-Gen: 50% With MA: 28% Completing MA: 14%	Undergraduate: BEEd-ECE: 40% FLCD: 10% BEEd-SpEd: 10% BS-Psych: 10% With MA: 28%
Average years of teaching experience	14 years	5 years
Status	100% full-time	100% full-time
Tenure	93% permanent	100% permanent

Instrumentation

The focus of this study was primarily to identify and evaluate the assessment practices of the classroom reading teachers from Kinder to Grade 3 in accordance with the Standards for the Assessment of Reading and Writing formulated by the NCTE and the IRA and informed by the fourteen domains of literacy emphasized by the Department of Education for literacy instruction in the K–12 program. A questionnaire was developed to generate data on the aspects of reading assessment articulated in the research questions, namely: 1) the frequency of the teachers’ reading assessment of the 14 literacy domains; 2) the different types of literary assessments that the teachers use and how often they use them in the classroom; 3) the level in which they use the assessment types; and 4) how they use the assessment results.

These aspects of reading and literacy assessment were articulated in seven questions, which were aimed at generating answers to the research questions. The first four questions required the participants to respond based on a Likert scale, which reflected an estimate of how frequently the respondents conduct reading assessments, assess particular literacy domains, and use specific assessment types. The scale ranges from Never, During Periodic Tests, Quarterly, At Least Once a Month, At Least Once a Week, and Every Day.

Procedure

A letter of request or email was sent to each of the school administrators, with the attached questionnaire duly signed by the course adviser. This included both the dean of the College of Education as well as the respective principals of the laboratory and non-laboratory schools. When consent from the concerned administrators was received and the teachers were informed of the survey, the questionnaires were sent to the principals, who then handed them to the respondents and subsequently retrieved them. In the laboratory school, seventy-four percent, or fourteen of the nineteen teachers from Kindergarten to Grade 3 participated in the study. In the non-laboratory school, about sixty-six percent of the Kindergarten to Grade 3 faculty participated in the survey.

After the retrieval of the questionnaires, the data were collated, tabulated, and analyzed. Comparisons were drawn from the responses of teachers in laboratory and non-laboratory schools. These were then interpreted in light of the NCTE/IRA Revised Standards for the Assessment of Reading and Writing (2009). On this basis, generalizations and conclusions were drawn.

Results and Discussion

To address the six research questions explored in the study, seven questions were included in the questionnaire. The first question sought information on the frequency with which K–3 reading and literacy teachers conduct reading and literacy assessments in their classes. Both the laboratory and non-laboratory schools frequently conduct reading assessments. Forty-three percent of the teachers at the laboratory school conduct reading assessments at least once a week, and thirty percent do it daily, while seventy percent of the teachers in the non-laboratory school assess their students every day, and twenty percent do it at least once a week. It appears that the laboratory school does not assess the students as frequently as the non-laboratory school. Based on the observation of the researcher, this is probably because the approach used in the laboratory school is thematic, and children spent longer periods in the various centers, e.g., language and dramatics, science, math, computer technology, and creative arts. In such cases, the teacher can only focus on a few students at a time. This does not mean, however, that assessment is not done daily.

Research question 2 sought information on what domains are assessed by the respondents and the frequency of assessing these domains. The most frequently assessed domains in the Lab School are as follows: 1) oral language (93%); 2) handwriting (71%); 3) alphabet knowledge (64%); and 4) book and print knowledge, phonics, the inferential and integrative levels of reading comprehension, and grammar awareness, each being assessed daily by 50% of the respondents.

On the other hand, although the non-laboratory school also has oral language as the main frequently assessed domain, the other frequently assessed domains are exactly the same as those in the laboratory school. In the non-laboratory school, the other frequently assessed domains are as follows: 1) oral language (90%); 2) phonics (80%); 3) listening comprehension and grammar awareness, each being assessed daily by 70% of the teachers; and 4) vocabulary and phonological awareness, each being assessed every day by 60% of the teachers.

On the whole, it may be observed that among the fourteen domains, oral language development is the most frequently assessed, with ninety-three percent of teachers in the laboratory school assessing it every day and ninety percent of the respondents in the non-laboratory school assessing it daily. This is consistent with the results for question number 3: the type and frequency of assessment used. Oral recitation, or question and answer, is the most frequently used assessment type. It may therefore be said that recitation forms an integral part of the formative assessment of the students' reading ability in K–3, both in lab and non-lab schools. This finding is also consistent with the respondents' responses to question number 3.

Research question 3 sought to determine the assessment types used by teachers and the frequency with which they assess their students using each of the identified types. Oral recitation and teacher-made

tests are the more frequently used assessment types in both laboratory and non-laboratory schools. In the laboratory school, this is closely followed by portfolios, anecdotal records, teacher-made informal reading inventories, and commercial tests and exercises such as those in workbooks. Similarly, in non-laboratory schools, oral recitation and teacher-made tests are followed by commercial tests.

Oral recitation, or question and answer, is the most frequently used assessment type in both laboratory and non-laboratory schools. It may therefore be said that recitation forms an integral part of the formative assessment of the students' reading ability in K–3 in both schools. This finding is also consistent with the respondents' responses in question 5, which sought information on which level particular domains are tested. Teachers in both schools unanimously assess oral language and listening, starting at the kindergarten level.

On the other hand, miscue analysis is rarely used by the respondents in both schools. Portfolios are used by 64 percent of the respondents from the laboratory school at least once a week; however, they are rarely used by the respondents from the non-laboratory school. This marked difference may be explained by the varying approaches to instruction and assessment in the two schools. It is part of the practice in the laboratory school for teachers to present students' portfolios as references or evidence of students' progress during parent-teacher conferences. These portfolios are also handed to the parents along with the students' report cards at the end of the school year. Moreover, as a laboratory school, it is expected that the teachers model innovative assessment practices, which include efficient and effective use of portfolios in assessing reading development, especially among beginning readers.

In fact, Afflerbach and Cho (2001) stated that *“a fully developed portfolio assessment can provide the evolutionary means to measure the development of students' content area knowledge, high-level thinking skills and strategies, and interests related to reading and learning. In a formative manner, portfolios may assist students in reviewing their accomplishments and evaluating their learning. Through analysis of portfolios, teachers may conduct continuous monitoring of students' progress and conduct ongoing revision of their mental model of students, learning, teaching, and classroom actions”* (p. 498).

The results for research question 4 sought to determine the type and frequency of use of teacher-made tests in laboratory and non-laboratory schools. Recitation is assessed daily by about 85 percent of the teachers in the laboratory school. Similarly, eighty percent of teachers in non-laboratory schools assess oral recitation every day.

Both the laboratory and the non-laboratory schools frequently use recitation or question and answer to assess their students. This is consistent with the literacy domain they frequently assess, which is oral language. However, the majority of teachers in the non-laboratory school address matching types on a weekly basis. It is also significant to take note that more than half of the respondents from the non-laboratory school never use composition or essay-writing, and portfolios assess their students' literacy skills. In general, teachers do not often use anecdotal records, miscue analysis, and portfolios as assessment tools. This is probably because these procedures take a relatively longer time to complete and score compared to tests such as multiple choice, matching type, and completion, which may take quite some time to prepare but only take a short time to score.

Question 5 sought information on what levels of schooling teachers assess in specific domains considered crucial to the development of beginning literacy skills. This includes letter identification, phonological awareness, concepts about print, oral language and listening, decoding and word recognition, oral reading rate and fluency, comprehension and retelling, handwriting and composing, and attitudes about reading. It shows that teachers in the laboratory school assess all of the aforementioned skills from Kindergarten to Grade 3. However, emphasis is given to oral language and listening, phonological awareness, letter identification, decoding and word recognition, comprehension and retelling, and oral reading and fluency, especially at the lowest level of schooling. It also shows a similar practice among teachers in non-laboratory schools.

Both laboratory and non-laboratory schools assess all the literacy domains from kindergarten to grade 3. However, results from non-laboratory schools showed that the respondents felt that the basic literacy domains like letter identification, phonological awareness, and concepts about print should no longer be assessed at the grade three level.

Regarding with the assessment of reading comprehension levels, it is worth noting that fifty percent of the respondents from both the laboratory and non-laboratory schools assess the inferential level every day. Moreover, fifty percent of the respondents from the laboratory school also assess the integrative level of comprehension daily. It appears that while both the laboratory and non-laboratory schools assess higher-order thinking skills (HOTS), particularly the interpretative and inferential levels, the laboratory school emphasized the development of HOTS even at the kindergarten level.

Table 2. Levels of schooling the different levels of comprehension are assessed

Reading Comprehension Levels	Levels of Schooling							
	Kindergarten		Grade 1		Grade 2		Grade 3	
	Lab	Non-Lab	Lab	Non-Lab	Lab	Non-Lab	Lab	Non-Lab
Interpretative	5 (36%)	4 (40%)	5 (36%)	6 (60%)	7 (50%)	5 (50%)	5 (36%)	2 (20%)
Evaluative	6 (43%)	1 (10%)	7 (50%)	3 (30%)	7 (50%)	5 (50%)	8 (57%)	3 (30%)
Integrative	10 (71%)	5 (50%)	8 (57%)	4 (40%)	8 (57%)	6 (60%)	8 (57%)	4 (40%)
Creative	9 (65%)	2 (20%)	7 (50%)	3 (30%)	7 (50%)	6 (60%)	8 (57%)	4 (40%)

Finally, the sixth research question aimed to determine the purposes for which assessment results are used by the K-3 teachers in the study. Respondents from both laboratory and non-laboratory schools use the data gathered from assessment to primarily report students' progress through report cards (93% for the laboratory and 100% for the non-laboratory school); for determining which parents need to attend the parent-teacher conference (93% for the laboratory and 90% for the non-laboratory school); for improvement of instruction (86% for the laboratory and 100% for the non-laboratory school); to determine students requiring remediation (71% for the laboratory and 100% for the non-laboratory school); to determine what needs to be discussed with other teachers for the improvement of reading instruction (71% for the laboratory and 80% for the non-laboratory school); and as basis for curriculum revision (84% for the laboratory and 60% for the non-laboratory school).

Assessment aims to generate information so that informed judgments can be made about students' reading achievement and development and appropriate interventions may be designed and implemented. However, "*while all classroom reading assessment should be conducted to foster student reading development, assessment materials and procedures are most effective when they are carefully matched to specific purposes.*" Sadly, assessment is typically used only to serve "*a reporting function, bearing information about student performance or achievement.*" Not many teachers recognize the importance of assessments in "*motivating and encouraging students, and teaching students to do assessment for themselves*" (Afflerbach and Cho, 2011; Afflerbach, 2018).

The data seems to show that although most of the teachers in the two schools use assessment data for reporting purposes, they are also keenly aware of its importance as data that could be used as a basis for the improvement of instruction and for the curriculum revision. This is consistent with Standard 3, which states that "*the primary purpose of assessment is to improve teaching and learning.*" It further stresses that although "*assessment is used in educational settings for a variety of purposes, such as keeping track of learning, diagnosing, reading and writing difficulties, determining eligibility for programs, evaluating programs, evaluating teaching, and reporting to others, underlying all these purposes is a basic concern for improving teaching and learning.*"

Conclusions and Recommendations

The first statement in the NCTE-IRA Revised Standards for the Assessment of Reading and Writing highlights the importance of considering the nature of the students in the preparation and conduct of assessment procedures. Standard 1 states: “*The interests of the student are paramount in assessment. Assessment experiences at all levels, whether formative or summative, have consequences for students.*” Contrary to this, Standard 7 states that “*the consequences of an assessment procedure are the first and most important consideration in establishing the validity of the assessment.*” This standard emphasized the importance of assessing the purposes of assessment and determining if there is a match between the purposes of assessment and the type, procedure, and content of the assessment activity.

In this study, the researchers assume that the construct being assessed by the Kindergarten to Grade 3 teachers, beginning reading and writing, is defined within the broader context of fourteen domains of literacy, as explicitly articulated by the Department of Education. The findings suggest that indeed, the teachers from both the laboratory and non-laboratory schools are aware of the importance of these literacy domains and have, in fact, assessed them, albeit with varying frequency.

It may be concluded that although the respondents from the laboratory and non-laboratory schools share similar reading assessment practices in that they 1) assess students’ reading skills on a daily basis; 2) assess similar reading and literacy domains with comparable frequency and at similar levels of schooling; and 3) use the assessment results for primarily the same purposes, they differ in that the laboratory school emphasized the assessment of higher levels of reading comprehension starting from the Kindergarten level. This is probably because laboratory schoolteachers or classes are often observed by preservice teacher education students and student teaching supervisors, who act as student teaching mentors. Thus, they are expected to model specific literacy instruction and assessment practices (Anderson et al., 2019).

In relation to the standards for assessment, respondents from both schools seem to recognize the important role of assessment in relation to the improvement of teaching and learning (Standard #3) and for curriculum review and improvement (Standard #4). Given the multiplicity of test types and forms of assessment used by teachers to generate data on students’ achievement vis-à-vis the literacy domains they consider to be crucial at particular stages of schooling, it appears that the respondents in both schools have attempted to meet Standard #8, which requires multiple perspectives and data sources for any judgment made on students. Finally, given that most of the respondents claim that the main reason for assessment is to report students’ achievement to parents, one may say that both schools have attempted to meet Standards 10 and 11.

On the other hand, it may be observed that parents and other stakeholders have not been involved in the assessment process other than as receivers of the assessment results. This appears contrary to Standard 10, which states that “*all stakeholders in the educational community—students, families, teachers, administrators, policymakers, and the public—must have an equal voice in the development, interpretation, and reporting of assessment information.*” This is something that needs to be considered by the administrators, teachers, and other stakeholders in the students’ literacy development. On the other hand, in the Philippine context, parents may opt to vest such responsibility in teachers and prefer the role of being recipients of the assessment results and the consequences that accompany such results, such as the implementation of reading intervention sessions. In the end, all these stakeholders must engage in a dialogue on the what, how, and why of the assessment of reading and writing for the best interest of the children (Bañez & Urayan, 2019).

Moreover, Standard #5 states that “*assessment must... reflect the intellectually and socially complex nature of reading and writing*” may be achieved by looking at the terms of the test as well as the assessment procedure. Although the laboratory school respondents claim that they assess higher levels of reading comprehension, a thorough analysis of a sample of tests and other assessment procedures is necessary to validate such claims. On the other hand, the non-laboratory school may want to consider encouraging their teachers to go beyond the literal level of reading comprehension in both literacy

instruction and assessment since theories of reading have emphasized the need to provide students' engagement opportunities where they could respond to the text in the context of their schemata or experiences.

On the whole, it may be said that the K-3 teachers in both laboratory and non-laboratory schools have met some of the assessment materials but need to improve on some aspects. Perhaps there is also a need for the teachers to familiarize themselves with the NCTE-IRA Standards for the Assessment of Reading and Writing Abilities and reflect on their relevance and applicability in their local contexts. Moreover, since private schools do not directly benefit from trainings on current innovations, policies, and discourses at the Department of Education, it may be suggested that literacy specialists from DepEd be invited to discuss recent innovations such as the teaching and assessment of the fourteen domains of literacy, especially in the early grades.

Finally, one must bear in mind that there is more to literacy assessment than the testing of reading subskills or discrete domains. As Calkins (2001) aptly puts it, "*what really matters in reading assessment are things that cannot be mandated; matching readers with books, understanding readers' habits, values, and self-perceptions, determining the strategies and sources of information that individual readers use and do not use, and their problem solving, critical and creative thinking skills. The more that politicians and administrators try to mandate and specify these things, the narrower the goals become. Assessing readers does not mean simply collecting data. It also means understanding the patterns in readers' behaviors and the logic behind what they are doing so that teachers can make moment-to-moment informed decisions*" (as cited by Campbell, 2001).

References

- Afflerbach, P. (2018). *Understanding and using reading assessment, K-12* (3rd ed.). ASCD.
- Afflerbach, P. P., & Cho, B. Y. (2011). The classroom assessment of reading. In M. L. Kamil, P. D. Pearson, E. B. Moje, & P. Afflerbach, *Handbook of reading research, volume IV* (pp. 487-514). Routledge.
- Anderson, K. L., Atkinson, T. S., Swaggerty, E. A., & O'Brien, K. (2019). Examining relationships between home-based shared book reading practices and children's language/literacy skills at kindergarten entry. *Early Child Development and Care, 189*(13), 2167-2182. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03004430.2018.1443921>
- Bañez, R. M., & Urayan, M. T. M. (2019). Unpacking pupils' reading ability: Examining the effect of Marungko approach-based intervention program for non-reader pupils. *International Journal of Recent Innovations in Academic Research, 3*(2), 60-66. <https://www.ijriar.com/index.php/ijriar/article/view/160/155>
- Calkins, L. M. (2001). *The art of teaching reading*. Addison-Wesley Longman.
- Campbell, M. B. (2001). Inquiry into reading assessment: Teachers' perceptions of effective practices. *Reading Horizons: A Journal of Literacy and Language Arts, 42*(1), 1-20. https://scholarworks.wmich.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1177&context=reading_horizons
- Education Development Center, Inc. (EDC). (2018, July 31). *USAID/Philippines Basa Pilipinas Program – Final project report: Annexes*. United States Agency for International Development. https://pdf.usaid.gov/pdf_docs/PBAAJ726.pdf
- IRA/NCTE Joint Task Force on Assessment, International Reading Association, & National Council of Teachers of English. (2009). *Standards for the assessment of reading and writing* (Revised ed.). International Reading Association, Inc. and National Council of Teachers of English.
- Smith, F. (2004). *Understanding reading: A psycholinguistic analysis of reading and learning to read* (6th ed.). Routledge.
- Venezky, R. L. (1987). A history of the American reading textbook. *The Elementary School Journal, 87*(3), 247-265. <https://doi.org/10.1086/461493>